

NDAC/LO/145
May 6, 1993

HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XVIIa
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This is a first status report for the '1.5-year' DS-reductions. The 'Case History Files' for 37476 systems have been successfully derived and comparisons with sphere solution data indicate that any remaining systematic errors are well below the 1 mas-level.

1. CHF-derivation

The CHF-generation uses some 10 different programs in a complex chain (cf. NDAC/LO/132, 141). Several of these programs have been revised, and most importantly, a major bug in the geometric calibrations has been corrected. Using a DAT tape-station with large storage-capacity, the whole chain is now also 'administratively' easier to go through. A preliminary round (with an incomplete photometric calibration) was run through last December, giving a set of CHF:s that was actually used for preliminary tests and optimizations. This March/April, the 'final' runs have been completed, using new photometric calibrations from RGO. (As in the main FAST and NDAC 18-month solutions, data from orbits # 1 - 1336 are included, with a non-corrected loss only of orbit # 658).

As an aid in comparing with the sphere solution data, a number of 'bona fide singles' (with the standard 'non-single' criterion in the middle of its range) was also selected. The criterion for 'suspected non-singles' was still set to flag a large number of systems, and the final CHF-count is 10500 known doubles, 497 known multiples, 10647 suspected non-singles and 15832 'singles', a total of 265 Mb. The CHF-derivation is still 'messy' (with frequent I/O to/from the DAT), but it is now more or less a routine procedure.

The complexity of the CHF-generation makes it however still very important to verify its correctness. This can be done by comparing the DS solutions (from CHF-data) and sphere solution results (from the three-stage process using great-circle 'abscissae' not used at all in the double star reductions). Agreeing solution results is strong evidence for the basic correctness of both the CHF-generation and the actual DS solution-procedures.

2. Sphere solution comparisons for single stars

The 'single' CHF:s were run through the SEEKDBL program, both to check for 'spurious' double-solutions and to get a large number of single-star solutions. Several runs of SEEKDBL have been made with different optimizations for the double-star detection, but the great majority of single-star solutions are unchanged. A comparison with NDAC's 'standard' 18-month solution gives typically almost 15000 common objects, and the raw statistics of the parameter differences are summarized in Table 1. (The comparison is for the mid-epoch of observation for each individual object, giving minimal position-sigmas).

Table 1. Statistics for the differences between the DS- and sphere solution results for stars with H_p -magnitudes < 7 , $7-10$ and >10 respectively. The means and std deviations are given in mas, while the normalized differences have been divided by the (sphere solution) σ . A few (nexcl) deviations larger than 5σ are excluded.

$H_p < 7$						
Parameter	n	nexcl	mean	std dev	norm	std dev
α	1354	6	-.03	1.19	-.03	0.90
δ	1358	2	-.02	0.94	-.02	0.88
π	1357	3	.05	1.36	.03	0.84
μ_α	1351	9	-.13	2.67	-.09	0.94
μ_δ	1349	11	-.01	2.51	.00	1.04
$H_p = 7 - 10$						
Parameter	n	nexcl	mean	std dev	norm	std dev
α	12198	13	.05	1.17	.02	0.73
δ	12201	10	.01	0.96	.01	0.72
π	12198	13	-.04	1.38	-.02	0.69
μ_α	12187	24	-.07	2.81	-.04	0.79
μ_δ	12183	28	-.03	2.52	-.01	0.83
$H_p > 10$						
Parameter	n	nexcl	mean	std dev	norm	std dev
α	1400	5	.04	1.63	.01	0.70
δ	1400	5	.05	1.47	.03	0.75
π	1400	5	-.04	2.07	-.02	0.69
μ_α	1403	2	.17	4.24	.03	0.77
μ_δ	1397	8	-.20	3.81	-.05	0.83

In the above table, the σ -values used for the normalized distributions are those given in the sphere solution (see below), and the (few) points deviating by more than 5σ have been discarded. The key points to note are the near zero mean differences in all parameters, and the smaller than unity normalized mean deviations.

In NDAC/LO/141, I uncovered a systematic difference between the covariances (for the astrometric parameters) calculated in the DS-processing and in the sphere solution. The diagonal terms in the covariance matrix were found to be too small in the DS-reductions, by roughly $\text{const}/\text{nscan}$, where nscan is the number of appreciably different scanning-directions used in the reductions. The constant was a reasonable $(4-5 \text{ mas})^2$, probably deriving from systematic along-scan attitude errors. In the present runs, similar effects remain obvious, and I have tried to derive corrective procedures in order to have mean DS covariances in agreement with the sphere solution.

Ideally, the 'observed' covariances for the calibrated IDT-parameters given in a CHF should be increased by a term expressing the phase-uncertainty due to attitude errors. One could try to introduce an attitude uncertainty of some

6-7 mas in each observation, giving modified (lower) observational weights. This indeed gives agreeing covariances in the DS and sphere solutions, *but* comparisons like the one in Table 1 then give a poorer agreement (larger dispersions) for the parameters. In reality, the attitude errors are not independent, but tend to be the same for all FOV-crossings with about the same geometry, and the modelling of such correlated errors seems difficult.

A simple method that works excellently for single stars is obtained by realizing that the covariances scale roughly as $1/nscan$, and that the covariance *ratios* (sphere sol/DS) are then roughly constant with $nscan$. The neglected attitude-errors in the DS-reductions then show up as a significant magnitude-dependence for the covariance-ratios. To correct, one may simply multiply the DS covariances by a single function of magnitude (f_c), giving in the mean a $\pm 10\%$ agreement with the sphere solution values. (A typical such function is the following

$$\lg f_c(H_p) = \begin{cases} 2.03 - 0.17H_p & H_p < 5 \\ 1.18 - 0.205(H_p - 5) & 5 < H_p < 8 \\ 0.57 - 0.191x + 0.027x^2 - 0.0017x^3 & x \equiv H_p - 8 > 0 \end{cases}$$

showing clearly that *large* factors are required for the brightest stars). The problem with this approach is that for real doubles, the 'normal' covariances are enlarged due to 'true' duplicity effects. For bright stars, the final covariances will be much 'overcorrected', and of course the whole principle with *multiplication* of covariances is questionable.

Fig 1. Ratio of (corrected) DS and sphere solution parallax covariances as function of the H_p -magnitude.

I have instead returned to the *addition* of $C_i/nscan$ -terms to the diagonal DS covariances (while keeping the correlations unchanged). This is in principle superior to the multiplication above, but in practice it is difficult to get a perfect fit to the sphere solution results. With $C_i = 12, 10, 18$ (mas)² in α, δ and π , 56 and 52 (mas/yr)² in μ_α and μ_δ , there are no magnitude-equations, but the mean

DS covariances are lower than the sphere solution ones by 10-25%. (If the C_i -values are increased, the covariances for the brightest stars increase too much, and we get a 'magnitude-equation' with the opposite slope). I therefore multiply also *all* the DS covariances by a standard factor 1.2. Fig 1 shows the final fit for the parallaxes. Similar plots (with *no* apparent magnitude-dependence) are obtained for the other parameters also. (It is important to make the above corrections to the 'minimal' position covariances at the observation epoch. If the additions are made at another epoch, new subtle systematic differences appear.)

3. Sphere solution comparisons for wide doubles

An even more important test comparison is for wide doubles ($\rho > 10$ arcsec), where the components have been independently observed. For some of these (not all, because they are by definition avoided in the sphere solution!) there are (disturbed) sphere solution results, and these are now compared with rigorous double-star reductions for the components taken together. Comparisons could be made for 978 individual components, and the normalized deviations ($\Delta par/\sigma$) in all five astrometric parameters are plotted in Fig 2 against $\Delta m_e = \Delta m + \Delta m(IFOV)$, where $\Delta m(IFOV)$ is the IFOV attenuation at the component separation. As expected, the results agree very well for Δm_e larger than about 4-5, while for smaller values (larger disturbances!), the sphere-solution is unreliable. (Quantitatively, the normalized deviations for $\Delta m_e > 4.5$ have means smaller than about 0.1, and standard deviations around unity).

Fig 2. Differences between the sphere and DS solutions for components of wide doubles.

A very interesting question is now to what extent the sphere solution covariances can be reproduced. At first, only the above $C_i/nscan$ corrections were added to the 'absolute' DS covariances (for the relative data, the attitude errors should have no influence), and then the whole covariance-matrix was multiplied by 1.2 (as before). When the covariances were then compared (for the solutions with $\Delta m_e > 4.5$), the values for the primary components were generally as similar as

for the singles. For secondary components with $\Delta m \sim 0$, the covariances turned out somewhat too small. (They *should* of course be equal to the covariances for their primaries). As a useful remedy, the relative DS covariances were multiplied by 1.8 (instead of the original 1.2), that is, they are increased by 50% relative to the 'absolute' data. The cause for this increase is unknown, and the factor is not very well-determined. *With* the corrections, the DS and sphere solution covariances are satisfactorily similar, however, as may be seen e.g. in Fig. 3. The points plotted are the 208 primaries and 45 secondaries with $\Delta m_e > 4.5$, and the spread of the covariance-ratios are not very much larger than for the single stars above.

Fig 3. Ratio of (corrected) DS and sphere solution covariances (for all five astrometric parameters) as function of the H_p -magnitude. Crosses are for primary components and circles for secondary components, all with the 'other' component effectively weakened by more than 4.5 magnitudes.

4. Conclusions

The main conclusion from the above comparisons is that the Case History Files derived by NDAC do contain relevant and correct data for further DS reductions. The agreement with the independent sphere solution results indicate that any systematic errors are at or below the 0.1 mas level, *and* that reliable DS solution covariances may be obtained by relatively simple (although partly ad hoc) procedures. More details and results from the DS reductions proper will be given in a sequel report.